

The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly: Examining Policy Developments on Cross Border Data Transfers and Digital trade in Nigeria

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AfCFTA – African Continental Free Trade Area
AGF – Attorney General of the Federation
CbDT – Cross-border Data Transfer
NDPC – Nigeria Data Protection Commission
DTP – Digital Trade Protocol
GDP – Gross Domestic Product
IMF – International Monetary Fund
MSMEs – Medium, Small, and Micro Enterprises
NITDA – National Information and Technology Development Agency
NDPA – Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023
NDPR – Nigeria Data Protection Regulation 2019
ICT – Information, Communication, and Technology
OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
WTO – World Trade Organisation

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Imagine these numbers:

- 150 million young people.¹
- 100 million Internet users.²
- An Information, Communication, and Technology (ICT) sector projected to generate US\$18.3 billion by 2026.³

With its teeming youth population, spread of digital connectivity, and sheer size and productivity of its ICT sector, Nigeria clearly dominates Africa's digital economy – and where digital economies flourish, digital trade thrives. Businesses and individuals migrate from physical stores to online shops, contracts are negotiated and concluded virtually; and transactions become borderless. However, with borderless transactions comes cross-border transfer of consumer's personal data and along with it, the risks of violating consumers' constitutionally guaranteed right to privacy.⁴

This essay will succinctly examine the policy developments on cross-border data transfer and digital trade in Nigeria in light of its potential impacts on data privacy. The concepts of cross-border data transfer and digital trade will be highlighted; followed by a critical analysis of the policy developments, and finally recommendations will be provided for policymakers.

2.0. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Cross Border Data Transfer: This can be defined as the movement of personal data from one state/jurisdiction to another. CbDT can be regarded as the lifeblood of the digital economy – as one author opines "*data is the fuel upon which the digital economy thrives.*"⁵ In this sense, data is not only a trade facilitator but also a tradable asset.⁶ However, as not all states have adequate mechanisms for data

¹ Agbonkhese Oboh, 'International Youth Day: 151 million Nigerians clicking for their future' (*Vanguard*, 12 August 2024)

<<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2024/08/international-youth-day-151-million-nigerians-clicking-for-their-future/>> accessed 28 September 2024.

² Ibid

³ Samson Akintaro, 'Nigeria's digital economy to generate \$18.3 billion by 2026 – Bosun Tijani' (*Nairametrics*, 10 July 2024)

<<https://nairametrics.com/2024/07/10/nigerias-digital-economy-to-generate-18-3-billion-by-2026-bosun-tijani/>> accessed 28 September 2024.

⁴ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended); Section 37

⁵ Victoria Oloni, 'Cross-Border Data Flows: Oiling the Wheel of the African Digital Economy' in Alex B Makulilo (ed), *African Data Protection Laws* (De Gruyter 2023)

<<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110797909-010>> accessed 28 September 2024.

⁶ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 'Digital Trade' (*OECD*, 2024)

<<https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/policy-issues/digital-trade.html>> accessed 28 September 2024.

protection, challenges arise when personal data is moved from a country with strong data protection frameworks to one that does not.

2.2. Digital Trade: According to the World Trade Organisation, digital trade "*refers to all international trade digitally ordered and/or digitally delivered.*"⁷ This definition alludes to three components of digital trade: digital ordering of goods and services; digital delivery of goods and services; and a necessary cross-border element in either the digital ordering or delivering. In this sense, cross-border data transfer "*underpins digital trade*".⁸

3.0. POLICY DEVELOPMENTS ON CROSS BORDER DATA TRANSFERS AND DIGITAL TRADE IN NIGERIA

3.1. OVERVIEW OF POLICY DEVELOPMENTS ON CROSS BORDER DATA TRANSFERS

The Tinubu-led administration has championed two major policy developments on CbDT in Nigeria in the past one year: assenting to the Nigeria Data Protection Bill 2023; and the policy adoption of AfCFTA's Digital Trade Protocol.

a. The Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023

Prior to the NDPA, CbDTs were regulated by the 2019 Nigeria Data Protection Regulation which provided two conditions for CbDT: one, a decision by NITDA with the supervision of the Attorney General of the Federation as to the adequacy of data protection measures in the foreign country; and where such adequacy decision was unavailable, by fulfilling any of the conditions laid out in Paragraph 2.12 such as obtaining informed consent of the data subject or where transfer is necessary to perform a contract.⁹

However, with the coming into force of the NDPA, CbDT is prohibited by default.¹⁰ The conditions under the NDPA 2019 for CbDT to occur are now exceptions to this general rule; and even then, with some modifications. A key point of difference is **that decision-making on the adequacy of data protection measures in the foreign country is now decentralised**. The NDPA makes it the responsibility of businesses and individuals collecting/transferring personal data (I.e data controllers) to assess the adequacy of data protection framework in the destination country.¹¹ The only point of regulatory intervention is that the newly created Nigeria

⁷ .. This definition flowed from OECD's as "trade in goods and services that are digitally ordered or delivered." – without reference to the trade being necessarily international trade; *ibid*.

⁸ OECD, *ibid*

⁹ Nigeria Data Protection Regulation 2019, paras 2.11-2.12.

¹⁰ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Section 41(1).

¹¹ *Ibid*

Data Protection Commission may issue guidelines or binding rules and codes of conduct to aid such decision-making; and may also make regulations enabling it to supervise the process of the decision-making of data controllers.¹² In effect, the **NDPC seems to have absolutely displaced NITDA and AGF as the regulatory agency for CbDT in Nigeria.**

b. (AfCFTA)'s Digital Trade Protocol

Given Nigeria's out-sized role in driving the digital revolution in Africa, the country's federal government in July 2024 unveiled its plan to implement the AfCFTA's Digital Trade Protocol (DTP) to further accelerate digital trade within the continent.¹³ The DTP had earlier been adopted at the 37th African Union Heads of State Summit in February 2024 as an integral aspect of the AfCFTA, and by extension, Agenda 2063 of the African Union.¹⁴ Through the harmonised framework it establishes, the DTP is positioned to stimulate digital trade and transformation in order to promote sustainable socio-economic development in the continent.¹⁵

With regards to CbDT, Article 20 of the Protocol **obliges states to implement open CbDT measures to allow unrestricted data flow across the continent** especially where the activity is related to digital trade by a person within a state-party to the AfCFTA. In essence, by opting to implement the DTP, the current administration might be signaling a desire to transition Nigeria from the conditional CbDT approach of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which our legal framework is modeled after to an open approach, following the lead of countries like United States of America and Canada.¹⁶

3.2. THE GOOD: POSITIVE IMPLICATIONS FOR NIGERIA(NS)

1. Rapid Socio-Economic Gains

Generally, the policy developments in CbDT in Nigeria are progressive and would largely promote digital trade in the country, which is very essential given the current state of the economy. A policy analysis conducted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) projected that by implementing the AfCFTA's DTP, Nigeria's

¹² Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Section 42 (3)-(5); 41(3).

¹³ Osamu Ekhaton, 'Nigeria launches roadmap to accelerate digital trade in Africa' (Techpoint Africa, 22 July 2024) <<https://techpoint.africa/2024/07/22/nigeria-launches-roadmap-digital-trade/>> accessed 28 September 2024.

¹⁴ Kariuki Muigua, 'Examining the African Continental Free Trade Area Protocol on Digital Trade: Challenges and Promises' (Kariuki Muigua & Co, May 2024) <<http://kmco.co.ke/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Examining-the-African-Continental-Free-Trade-Area-Protocol-on-Digital-Trade-Challenges-and-Promise-x-1.pdf>> accessed 28 September 2024

¹⁵ Protocol to the Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area on Digital Trade., Available at https://www.bilaterals.org/IMG/pdf/afcfta_digital_trade_protocol_-_9_february_2024_draft.pdf Article 2

¹⁶ Oloni, *ibid* n.5, used the terms "open transfer approach" and "conditional transfer approach" to juxtapose the CbDT of the North American countries and European systems respectively.

GDP could increase by over 11% and grow at a rate of 15% per annum, with exports accelerating to over US\$ 79 billion.¹⁷ In addition, over 10 million jobs could be created.¹⁸

2. Fostering Ease of Doing Business

With Nigeria currently ranked 131 of 190 countries in the ease of doing business,¹⁹ urgent interventions are needed to eliminate bottlenecks that businesses face; and the NDPA does this by decentralising decision-making for CbDT. Unlike before, businesses conducting digital trade across borders no longer need to resort to NITDA or the AGF to ascertain whether or not the destination country has an adequate data protection framework. Moreover, even where the destination country does not have adequate data protection measures, one of the conditions where CbDT is still possible is where it is made in performance of a contract – and digital trades would likely fall within this provision.

3.2. THE BAD: HOW NIGERIA'S DIGITAL TRADE MIGHT SUFFER

The current legal and policy direction on CbDT is fraught with uncertainty, which might affect regulatory efficiency and of course, the willingness of investors to step in. First, the NDPR exists side by side with the NDPA,²⁰ and as such the list of countries who have been "certified" to have adequate mechanisms for data protection drawn up under the NDPR is still in use despite its controversies for including countries without data protection regulatory bodies.²¹ Second, the supervisory roles of the regulatory bodies under the NDPR and NDPA are yet to be settled, with the closest clarity coming from Section 7 of the NDPA 2023 which provides for the independence of NDPC in performing its functions. Even then, would this mean it exercises its supervisory role concurrently with the AGF? Third, with the introduction of the AfCFTA DTP, economic actors are left to wonder what impact this could have on Section 41 of the NDPA 2023 on CbDT, despite that the latter has statutory flavour.

3.3. THE UGLY: HOW NIGERIA'S CITIZENS MAY SUFFER

¹⁷ Agarwal, Prachi 'The digital ecosystem in Nigeria and the AfCFTA Digital Trade Protocol: raising awareness and strategising implementation.' (July 2024) *ODI Policy Brief*. London: ODI
<<https://odi.org/en/publications/advancing-implementation-of-the-afcfta-protocol-on-digital-trade-in-nigeria>> accessed 28 September 2024

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/ease-of-doing-business>

²⁰ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Section 64(2)(f)

²¹ Uche Val Obi, 'Cross-Border Data Transfer: Navigating Compliance under the Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023' (INPLP, 11 October 2023)
<<https://inplp.com/latest-news/article/cross-border-data-transfer-navigating-compliance-under-the-nigeria-n-data-protection-act-2023/>> accessed 28 September 2024.

The primary criticism of Nigeria's current legal and policy developments is rooted in its insufficient consideration of the data privacy of its most vulnerable citizens. Neither the NDPR or the NDPA 2023 make any special provisions for the CbDT of sensitive data – with the NDPA going as far as allowing CbDT obtained without consent of the data subject on the grounds that it is for their sole benefit and "*if it were reasonably practicable to obtain the consent of the data subject, they would likely give it*"!²²

Regarding the DTP, this essay adopts Sucker's²³ argument that big tech companies operating within Africa can take advantage of the open CbDT approach offered under the DTP to exploit consumer's personal data. After all, Meta flouted Nigeria's restricted CbDT laws with impunity.²⁴

4.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

While CbDT is vital for digital trade and hence economic growth, it must be well-regulated to ensure that data privacy rights are not sacrificed on the altar of economic benefits. Thus, the following recommendations for harmonised policy action could bolster digital trade while protecting data privacy:

1. There has to be clear delineation of the roles of the NDPC, NITDA, AGF under the current regime.
2. The conflict between the provisions of the NDPA and AfCFTA's DTP with regards to CbDT with state-parties to the AfCFTA should be formally resolved in favour of the NDPA; and if not, the necessary legislative amendments should be effected with sufficient protection for Nigerian citizens.
3. Special protection for sensitive data during CbDT has to be provided – and Section 43(1)(c) of the NDPA 2023 should be reviewed.

²² Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Section 43(1)(c)

²³ Franziska Sucker, 'Digital trade protocol for Africa: why it matters, what's in it and what's still missing' (The Conversation, 31 March 2024)

<<https://theconversation.com/digital-trade-protocol-for-africa-why-it-matters-whats-in-it-and-whats-still-missing-225908>> accessed 28 September 2024.

²⁴ Ifeoma Joy Okorie, 'FCCPC asserts its orders against WhatsApp are based on legitimate concerns' (Techpoint Africa, 2 August 2024)

<<https://techpoint.africa/2024/08/02/fccpc-orders-meta-legitimate-concerns/>> accessed 2 August 2024.